

A Successful Osteoplastic Reconstruction Of Thumb in Immediate Setting in a Patient With High Voltage Electric Injury (HVEI). A Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Electrical burn injuries are different than thermal injuries in their peculiar pathophysiology and usually damage both the overlying skin and the deeper tissues, especially the underlying bones, thus frequently ending in amputations. Type and timing of tissue reconstruction in patients with electrical burns is crucial to achieve the optimal results. We report a 28 old male who developed dry gangrene of the thumb following high voltage electric injury (HVEI) and in whom we performed primary osteoplastic thumb reconstruction using a corticocancellous iliac bone graft as skeletal support and reverse radial artery forearm fasciocutaneous flap (RRAFF) for soft tissue cover.

Keywords: Burn; Osteoplastic; Reconstruction; Graft; Flap

INTRODUCTION

Although electrical burn injuries comprise only 3–7% of all burn patients^[1-6] but these injuries are usually destructive secondary to the progressive damage to the skin and deeper tissues thereby risking the limb function and eventually ending in amputation. Pathogenesis of electrical injuries is different from thermal burns in that the tissue damage after electrical injury is mediated either electrically or thermally or by the combination of the two and continues even after the cessation of the electric current. Thermal injury results in coagulative necrosis of tissue due to the heat generated when the current comes in contact with resistance^[3,7] whereas the non-thermal direct electrical injury causes electroconformational changes in membrane proteins, and the formation of pores in the cell membrane (i.e. electroporation).^[2,6,8,9] Loss of limb either total or partial is a devastating complication of electric injury.

The timing of soft tissue reconstruction, whether immediate, intermediate or delayed, after electrical burns is crucial for proper outcome. Because the pathophysiology of electrical burns, characterized by progressive tissue

necrosis and denaturation of blood vessels the timing of limb reconstruction in patients with HVEI is still debatable.^[7,10]

The thumb alone forms about 40% of the hand functions. Hence loss of thumb results in significant loss of hand function^[11] as the thumb is an important contributor to the complex mechanism of prehension inflicting major disability unless reconstruction is performed. Different options of thumb reconstruction like pollicization, toe to thumb transfer, osteoplastic thumb reconstruction and free tissue transfer are the most reported procedures after traumatic amputation at the proximal and middle third of the thumb other than replantation.^[12] Osteoplastic reconstruction of the thumb is indicated in amputation at or around metacarpophalangeal level in patients who cannot, or will not, have a toe transfer.^[13] In our patient of HVEI we have successfully performed the primary osteoplastic thumb reconstruction using corticocancellous iliac bone graft for skeletal support and the reverse radial fasciocutaneous flap for soft tissue cover.

CASE REPORT

A 28-year-old right-handed male, medically free, non-smoker, and worker attended our Emergency Department as a case of accidentally sustained high voltage electric injury with entry wound on right hand and exit wounds left wrist. While resuscitating, the patient was simultaneously evaluated for any life-threatening injuries according to the latest advanced trauma life support (ATLS) protocol by the emergency physicians. Fluid resuscitation was started using normal saline and advised to titrate the input rate to maintain the urine output of 1.5ml per kg per hour. The patient received a single intramuscular dose of tetanus toxoid, broad-spectrum intravenous antibiotics, and multimodal analgesia. Blood samples were taken and sent for complete blood count (CBC), coagulation profile, kidney function tests including creatinine, urea and blood urea nitrogen (BUN), liver function tests (LFT), creatine phosphokinase (CPK), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), venous blood gas (VBG) and serum electrolytes and blood grouping with cross-matching. Urinolysis of urine for myoglobin was also performed. Local examination of the patient revealed an entry wound over the right hand involving the thumb and the thenar eminence and an exit wound over flexor aspect of the left wrist on the ulnar side. A prophylactic right forearm fasciotomy was performed in the emergency department. The patient was managed in the ward with daily dressing. The patient developed progressive gangrenous changes in his right thumb and the gangrene got completely demarcated within two weeks of the burn injury [Figure 1]. Under regional anaesthesia debridement of the dead soft tissue was done and the bones were checked for viability intra-operatively by paprika sign. All the dead bone was debrided leaving behind only around 1 cm of the healthy base of metacarpal with intact carpometacarpal (CMC) joint [Figure 2,8]. On the fifth post-operative day, a proper consent was taken after discussion with the patient about the further management plan regarding the immediate reconstruction of the thumb. Preoperatively, Allen's test was done using a hand held Doppler to confirm the patency of the palmar arch for the ulnar flow for harvesting the reverse radial forearm flap (RRFAF). Under general anaesthesia and tourniquet control, thorough debridement of the non-viable tissue was done. A corticocancellous bone graft $8 \times 1.5 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$ in size was harvested from the ipsilateral iliac crest and after absolute hemostasis the wound closed in layers after putting a 16 size suction drain [Figure 3,4,5]. Under C-arm guidance the harvested iliac bone graft was fixed to the remnant of the thumb metacarpal base using three 12

size K- wires in different planes with CMC joint in abduction, extension and with concavity of the graft opposing the palm.[Figure 9] A 12×8 cm² reverse radial artery fasciocutaneous flap (RRAFF) was designed on the forearm and raised in the sub fascial plane as an peninsular flap to cover the neo-thumb skelton.[Figure 6] Few hitch stitches were taken to anchor the flap uniformly to the bony skelton. The donor site was covered with a split-thickness skin graft (STSG) harvested from the left thigh [Figure 6]. At the end of the operation, the non-adherent dressing was used over all operative sites. Finally, a thumb spica was used to splint the thumb. Post operatively the flap monitoring was done by the clinical methods every 4 hourly for first day then six hourly for next 3 days. The first dressing change was done on the 5th postoperative day(POD), the skin graft was well taken. The suction drain was also removed. On 7th POD, after 2nd dressing, the patient was discharged and advised to follow up outpatient department (OPD) weekly for 2 months. K wires were removed after 2 months after x ray confirmation of the bone healing [Figure 9]. On follow-up, X-ray of the hand was repeated at 6 months and later at 9 months which showed intact bone graft without any signs of bone resorption and well healed bony union [Figure 10].

Figure 1: Preoperative photo of the right forearm and hand showing a healed post fasciotomy(prophylactic) wound with insitu sutures and gangrenous thumb secondary to HVEI.

Figure 2: Showing intraoperative picture of the right hand with absence of the thumb after surgical debridement.

Figure 3: Intra- operative picture showing marking for harvesting of right iliac bone graft.

Figure 4: Intra- operative picture showing the harvested corticocancellous iliac bone graft.

Figure 5: Intra- operative picture showing right hand with absence of thumb and 8cm long iliac bone graft.

Figure 6: Intra- operative picture showing the reconstructed osteoplastic thumb and split thickness skin grafting (meshed 1:1.5) of the secondary defect and an insitu glove drain.

Figure 7: Showing postoperative picture on 3 months follow-up of the reconstructed thumb with satisfactory hand-digital cylindrical grasp for large objects (photo sent by the patient).

Figure 8: Showing intraoperative X ray of right hand showing total amputation of the thumb with preserved CMC joint.

Figure 9: Intra-operative picture showing fixation of iliac bone graft to the metacarpal base using three 12 size K wires in different planes.

Figure 10: Post operative picture showing well healed bony union of the iliac bone graft with the base of first metacarpal bone on 6 months follow-up.

DISCUSSION

Reconstructive plastic surgery in patients with high-voltage injuries can be very heterogeneous.^[4] The timing of reconstruction in patients with HVEI is matter of debate as some authors are of the opinion that all tissue damage occurs at the time of sustaining the burn injury and immediately after thereby favouring immediate reconstruction including free tissue transfer.^[14] They give the reason that immediate reconstruction allows to salvage part of borderline damaged tissues and may minimise the tissue loss. While as other group of authors claim that the tissue necrosis is progressive after the initial burn injury sustained by the patient^[15] and an early tissue coverage may results in fluids collection, infection and eventually flap loss.^[14] Third group of authors claim that the timing of reconstruction did not appear to affect flap survival.^[16] These authors argue that the higher flap failure rate in early reconstruction is possibly because of suboptimal initial debridement than the timing of the reconstruction per se. In our patient we successfully performed thumb reconstruction in immediate setting using a iliac bone graft and reverse radial artery forearm flap(RRAFF) without any flap or bone graft related complications.

In patients who suffer loss of thumb following trauma, the choice of the reconstructive method is guided by the level of thumb amputation. Physical examination and radiographs are used for determination of level of loss.^[4] Among the different methods of thumb reconstruction although toe to thumb transfer is gold standard but osteoplastic

reconstruction is a very good alternative if mobility at carpometacarpal (CMC) joint is intact, because good opposition and grasp can be achieved with osteoplastic techniques with intact CMC joint. As most of these patients are manual labourers, hence stability, length, position and strength were most important factors to be achieved. In our patient these factors were very well attained by this method of reconstructive surgery [Figure 7]. Osteoplastic reconstruction, although inferior in cosmetic outcome, does not require sacrifice of another finger or a toe and also does not need microsurgical expertise.^[17,18] Besides this kind of method doesn't require expert microsurgical knowledge, which is important in case of replantation or revascularization of the amputated thumb or in toe transfer. Scar in the area of the harvested flap and its unsightly look are the donor site morbidities associated with the RRAFF besides sacrificing a main vessel of the hand which is usually safe for the hand viability when preoperative Allen's test is performed to know the patency of the vascular arches and the ulnar blood flow.

The resorption of the bone graft may be other complication associated with osteoplastic reconstruction. Hanawi M et al and Salah M.M et al in their respective cases did not find any resorption of the skeltanized phalyngeal cortical bone grafts used by them for thumb reconstruction even after one year follow up and have advocated the use bone grafts for thumb reconstruction.^[19,20] Similarly we didn't find any resorption of the iliac bone graft in our patient till 9 months follow-up.[Figure 10] The absence of sensitivity of the neo-thumb in osteoplastic reconstruction patients can be tackled by doing a neurosensory Littler flap which we counselled to our patient who had already returned back to his occupation and was able to use his thumb to earn livelihood.

CONCLUSIONS

HVEI has high amputation rate compared to thermal injuries. In patients with intact CMC joint following thumb amputation after a optimal surgical debridement immediate osteoplastic thumb reconstruction is a good option to restore satisfactory thumb function when planned meticulously.

Level of Evidence: IV

Conflict of interest: None declared

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